

Supplementary Material

CONTENTS

Contents	1
List of Tables	2
List of Listings	3
	3
A Full Description of the Problems Given to Participants	4
A.1 Problem A	4
A.2 Problem B	8
B Listings of Model Solutions to the Problems	13
B.1 Problem A Solutions	13
B.2 Problem B Solutions	17
C Screening survey	19
D Tutorial	20
E Programming Surveys	21
E.1 First Programming Survey	21
E.2 Second Programming Survey	22
F Listings of Participants Solutions to the Problems	24
G Tables of the Correlation Matrix for Participants' Data	29

LIST OF TABLES

C.1 Screening Survey	19
E.1 First Programming Survey	21
E.2 Second Programming Survey Plus Demographics	22
G.1 Correlation matrix for problem A	29
G.2 Correlation matrix for problem B	29

LIST OF LISTINGS

A.1	Full CPP File for Problem A	7
A.2	Full CPP File for Problem B	12
B.1	Our Naive Level 0 (L0) Solution to Problem A	13
B.2	Our Level 1 (L1) Solution to Problem A	14
B.3	Our Level 2 (L2) Solution to Problem A	15
B.4	Our Level 3 (L3) Solution to Problem A	16
B.5	Our Naive Level 0 (L0) Solution to Problem B	17
B.6	Our Level 1 (L1) Solution to Problem B	18
F.1	P11's L0 Solution to Problem B with Copilot	24
F.2	P12's L1 Solution to Problem B with Copilot	25
F.3	P17's L1 Solution to Problem B without Copilot	26
F.4	P19's L0 Solution to Problem B with Copilot	27
F.5	P22's L1U Solution to Problem A with Copilot	28
F.6	P24's L1 Solution to Problem B with Copilot.	30
F.7	P27's L1 Solution to Problem B with Copilot	31

A FULL DESCRIPTION OF THE PROBLEMS GIVEN TO PARTICIPANTS

A.1 Problem A

```
1  /**
2   * PLEASE READ ENTIRE FILE CAREFULLY BEFORE YOU BEGIN.
3   * Your goal in this exercise is to read
4   * many records from large text files and
5   * write them to a buffer. A record
6   * is a series of bytes in a large text file.
7   *
8   */
9
10 #include <algorithm>
11 #include <fstream>
12 #include <iostream>
13 #include <random>
14 #include <string>
15 #include <vector>
16
17 using namespace std;
18
19 /** The size of each record in bytes*/
20 #define RECORD_SIZE 5000
21
22 /** The number of records to read*/
23 #define NUM_RECORDS 500000
24
25 /** Global vector of strings which are the file names of some large text files
26  * in your working directory. You may assume that each file is at least 1GB (1e9
27  * bytes) in size and contains random text.
28  * Because it is impractical to send several 1GB files, we have provided 10MB
29  * (1e7 bytes) files instead for easier debugging
30  * DO NOT EDIT!
31  */
32 const std::vector<std::string> FILE_NAMES = {
33     "large_file_1.txt", "large_file_2.txt", "large_file_3.txt"};
34
35 /** The size of the file in bytes. Ideally this should be
36  * 1e9 bytes (1GB) but it is impractical to send out
37  * such a large file.
38  * DO NOT EDIT!
39  */
40 #define FILE_SIZE 1e7
41
42 /** A struct representing a file combination
43  * DO NOT EDIT!
```

```

44  */
45  struct FileCombo {
46      int fileId; /** A valid index in `FILE_NAMES` */
47      int offset; /** A valid seek position for a file at `FILE_NAMES[fileId]` */
48      char buffer[RECORD_SIZE + 1]; /** The output buffer */
49  };
50
51  std::vector<FileCombo> createCombos();
52  void sanityCheck(std::vector<FileCombo> &combos);
53
54  void readFileCombos(std::vector<FileCombo> &fileCombos);
55
56  /**
57   * Implement the `readFileCombos` function that reads all the records from the
58   * vector of file combinations `fileCombos` and writes each record to the
59   * `buffer` member of the `FileCombo` struct. Each record is `RECORD_SIZE`
60   * bytes. You may assume that reading `RECORD_SIZE` bytes from any file in
61   * `FILE_NAMES` starting at any seek position, `offset` in `fileCombos` will
62   * never throw an error.
63   *
64   */
65
66  /**
67   * Example
68   *
69   * * * * * example_file.txt * * * * *
70   * fourLetTextUsedHereAlsoHere
71   * * * * * EOF * * * * *
72   *
73   * * * * * program.cpp * * * * *
74   * #define RECORD_SIZE 4
75   * #define NUM_RECORDS 4
76   * const std::vector<std::string> FILE_NAMES = {"example_file.txt"};
77   *
78   * void readFileCombos(std::vector<std::string> &fileCombos,
79   *                     std::vector<char[RECORD_SIZE + 1]> &buffer);
80   *
81   * int main() {
82   *     std::vector<FileCombo> fileCombos = {
83   *         {.fileId = 0, .offset = 4, .buffer = ""},
84   *         {.fileId = 0, .offset = 20, .buffer = ""},
85   *         {.fileId = 0, .offset = 8, .buffer = ""},
86   *         {.fileId = 0, .offset = 24, .buffer = ""},
87   *     };
88   *     readFileCombos(&fileCombos);
89   *     return 0;

```

```

90  * }
91  * * * * * EOF * * * * *
92  *
93  * fileCombos is now
94  * {
95  *     {.fileId = 0, .offset = 4, .buffer = "Lett"},
96  *     {.fileId = 0, .offset = 20, .buffer = "Also"},
97  *     {.fileId = 0, .offset = 8, .buffer = "Text"},
98  *     {.fileId = 0, .offset = 24, .buffer = "Here"},
99  * }
100 *
101 */
102
103 void readFileCombos(std::vector<FileCombo> &fileCombos) {
104     // YOUR CODE GOES HERE
105 }
106
107 int main() {
108     // Main function
109     std::vector<FileCombo> fileCombos = createCombos();
110
111     readFileCombos(fileCombos);
112
113     // Uncomment the below line to test for correctness
114     sanityCheck(fileCombos);
115     return 0;
116 }
117 /**
118  * Generates vector of `FileCombo` structs of size `NUM_RECORDS`
119  * where each `fileId` member is a random index from `FILE_NAMES`
120  * and each `offset` member is a random valid seek position for the file at
121  * `FILE_NAMES[fileId]`.
122  * DO NOT EDIT!
123  */
124 std::vector<FileCombo> createCombos() {
125     std::random_device rd;
126     std::mt19937 gen(rd());
127     std::uniform_int_distribution<int> fileIdDis(0, FILE_NAMES.size() - 1);
128     std::uniform_int_distribution<int> offsetDis(0,
129         FILE_SIZE - (2 * RECORD_SIZE));
130
131     std::vector<FileCombo> combos;
132     for (int i = 0; i < NUM_RECORDS; ++i) {
133         FileCombo fc = {.fileId = fileIdDis(gen), .offset = offsetDis(gen), ""};
134         combos.push_back(fc);
135     }

```

```
136     return combos;
137 }
138
139 /**
140  * Checks that the `buffer` member of each `FileCombo` struct in `combos`
141  * is the correct record.
142  * DO NOT EDIT!
143  */
144 void sanityCheck(std::vector<FileCombo> &combos) {
145     printf("Running Sanity Checks...\n");
146     for (int i = 0; i < NUM_RECORDS; ++i) {
147         std::ifstream in;
148         in.open(FILE_NAMES[combos[i].fileId]);
149         in.seekg(combos[i].offset);
150         char temp[RECORD_SIZE + 1] = "";
151         in.read(temp, RECORD_SIZE);
152         in.close();
153         if (std::string(combos[i].buffer) != std::string(temp)) {
154             printf("combos[%d].fileId = %d\n", i, combos[i].fileId);
155             printf("combos[%d].offset = %d\n", i, combos[i].offset);
156             printf("combos[%d].buffer = %s\n", i, combos[i].buffer);
157             printf("instead of\ncombos[%d].buffer = %s\n", i, temp);
158             printf("Check Failed!\n");
159             return;
160         }
161     }
162     printf("All Checks passed!\n");
163 }
```

Listing A.1. Full CPP File for Problem A

A.2 Problem B

```
1  /**
2  * PLEASE READ ENTIRE FILE CAREFULLY BEFORE YOU BEGIN.
3  * Your goal in this exercise is to apply multithreaded programming to
4  * set all the values in a source array buffer to zero while setting all the
5  * values in a destination array buffer to a particular value. However, you are
6  * only allowed to increment or decrement the values in the respective array
7  * buffers. Assignment operations (move and copy) are not allowed on either the
8  * source array buffer or the destination array buffer.
9  *
10 * /
11
12 #include <algorithm>
13 #include <iostream>
14 #include <thread>
15
16 using namespace std;
17
18 /**
19 * The initial value of every `val` member in
20 * `src` array for the problem statement
21 *  $2^{17} = 131072$ 
22 * /
23 const int INIT_SRC_VAL = (1 << 17);
24
25 /**
26 * The size of the arrays in the problem statement
27 *  $2^{11} = 2048$ 
28 * /
29 const int SIZE = (1 << 11);
30
31 /**
32 * Number of threads you are permitted to use
33 * for the problem statement
34 * /
35 const int THREAD_COUNT = 4;
36
37 /**
38 * A struct containing an integer that can only
39 * be incremented or decremented.
40 * DO NOT EDIT!
41 * /
42 struct Item {
43     private:
44         /** Private integer member*/
```

```

45     int val;
46
47     /** Private Copy and Move Constructors
48      * to prevent move and copy operations
49      */
50     Item(const Item&);
51     Item(Item&&);
52     Item& operator=(const Item&);
53     Item& operator=(Item&&);
54
55     public:
56     Item() { val = 0; }
57     Item(int i) { val = i; }
58     /** Returns the integer member `val` */
59     int get() { return val; }
60
61     /** Increments the integer member `val` */
62     void operator++() { ++val; }
63     void operator++(int) { val++; }
64
65     /** Decrements the integer member `val` */
66     void operator--() { --val; }
67     void operator--(int) { val--; }
68 };
69
70 /**
71  * Global array of `Item` structs where each
72  * `val` member is initialized to `INIT_SRC_VAL`
73  */
74 Item src[SIZE];
75 void initSrc();
76
77 /**
78  * Global array of `Item` structs where each
79  * `val` member is initialized to 0
80  */
81 Item dst[SIZE];
82
83 void sanityCheck();
84
85 void schedule();
86 /**
87  * Using `THREAD_COUNT` threads, implement the function `schedule`
88  * which mutates the `val` member for each `Item` in `src` to 0 and the
89  * `val` member for each `Item` in `dst` to `INIT_SRC_VAL`. The `Item`
90  * struct only supports a `get()` method and increment and decrement operations

```

```
91 * and a few initialization constructors. See the `Item` struct for more details.
92 *
93 * `src[0]++`, `++src[0]`, `src[0]--` or `--src[0]` are valid.
94 * `dst[i]++`, `++dst[i]` `dst[0]--` or `--dst[0]` are also valid.
95 * `Item p = Item(54)` is valid.
96 * `Item items[4] = {Item(1), Item(2), Item(3), Item(4)}` is valid.
97 * `items[4] = items[3]` is not valid.
98 * `items[4] = Item(32)` is not valid.
99 * `src[0] = 0` or `dst[0] = INIT_SRC_VAL` or `Item temp = src[0]` or similar
100 * are not valid.
101 *
102 */
103
104 /**
105 * Example
106 *  $2^{10} = 1024$ 
107 *  $INIT\_SRC\_VAL = (1 \ll 10)$ 
108 *
109 *  $2^2 = 4$ 
110 *  $SIZE = (1 \ll 2)$ 
111 *
112 *
113 * Initial values for `src` and `dst`
114 * src = {
115 *   {.val = 1024},
116 *   {.val = 1024},
117 *   {.val = 1024},
118 *   {.val = 1024}
119 * }
120 *
121 * dst = {
122 *   {.val = 0},
123 *   {.val = 0},
124 *   {.val = 0},
125 *   {.val = 0}
126 * }
127 *
128 * Make the call to `schedule`
129 * schedule()
130 *
131 * Values for `src` and `dst` after `schedule` is called
132 * src = {
133 *   {.val = 0},
134 *   {.val = 0},
135 *   {.val = 0},
136 *   {.val = 0}
```

```
137 * }
138 *
139 * dst = {
140 *   {.val = 1024},
141 *   {.val = 1024},
142 *   {.val = 1024},
143 *   {.val = 1024}
144 * }
145 *
146 */
147
148 void schedule() {
149     // YOUR CODE GOES HERE
150 }
151
152 int main() {
153     // Main function
154     initSrc(); // DO NOT USE
155
156     schedule();
157
158     // Uncomment the line below to test for correctness
159     sanityCheck();
160     return 0;
161 }
162
163 /**
164  * Initializes the `val` member for each `Item` in `src`
165  * to `INIT_SRC_VAL`. Called in `main` once and never again.
166  * DO NOT EDIT or CALL!
167  */
168 void initSrc() {
169     for (int i = 0; i < SIZE; ++i) {
170         for (int j = 0; j < INIT_SRC_VAL; ++j) {
171             ++src[i];
172         }
173     }
174 }
175 /**
176  * Verifies that the `val` member for each `Item` in `src`
177  * is 0 and the `val` member for each `Item` in `dst`
178  * is `INIT_SRC_VAL`.
179  */
180 void sanityCheck() {
181     printf("Running Sanity Checks...\n");
182     bool isFail = false;
```

```
183 for (int i = 0; i < SIZE; ++i) {
184     if (src[i].get() != 0) {
185         printf("src[%d].get() = (%d) instead of (%d)\n", i, src[i].get(), 0);
186         isFail = true;
187     }
188     if (dst[i].get() != INIT_SRC_VAL) {
189         printf("dst[%d].get() = (%d) instead of (%d)\n", i, dst[i].get(),
190             INIT_SRC_VAL);
191         isFail = true;
192     }
193
194     if (isFail) {
195         printf("Check Failed!\n");
196         return;
197     }
198 }
199
200 printf("All Checks Passed!\n");
201 }
```

Listing A.2. Full CPP File for Problem B

B LISTINGS OF MODEL SOLUTIONS TO THE PROBLEMS

B.1 Problem A Solutions

```
1 void readFileCombos(std::vector<FileCombo> &fileCombos) {  
2     for(auto &fileCombo: fileCombos){  
3         ifstream in;  
4         in.open (FILE_NAMES[fileCombo.fileId], std::ios::binary);  
5         in.seekg(fileCombo.offset);  
6         in.read (fileCombo.buffer, RECORD_SIZE);  
7         in.close();  
8     }  
9 }
```

Listing B.1. Our Naive Level 0 (L0) Solution to Problem A

```
1 void readFileCombos(std::vector<FileCombo> &fileCombos) {
2     std::vector<ifstream> files(FILE_NAMES.size());
3     for (int i = 0; i < FILE_NAMES.size(); ++i) {
4         files[i].open(FILE_NAMES[i], std::ios::binary);
5     }
6     for (FileCombo & fc: fileCombos) {
7         files[fc.fileId].seekg(fc.offset);
8         files[fc.fileId].read(fc.buffer, RECORD_SIZE);
9     }
10    for (ifstream & f: files) {
11        f.close();
12    }
13
14 }
```

Listing B.2. Our Level 1 (L1) Solution to Problem A

```
1 void readFileCombos(std::vector<FileCombo> &fileCombos) {
2     std::sort(fileCombos.begin(), fileCombos.end(),
3         [](const FileCombo &a, const FileCombo &b) {
4             if (a.fileId != b.fileId) {
5                 return a.fileId < b.fileId;
6             }
7             return a.offset < b.offset;
8         });
9
10    for (FileCombo &fc : fileCombos) {
11        ifstream in;
12        in.open (FILE_NAMES[fileCombo.fileId], std::ios::binary);
13        in.seekg(fc.offset);
14        in.read(fc.buffer, RECORD_SIZE);
15        in.close();
16    }
17 }
```

Listing B.3. Our Level 2 (L2) Solution to Problem A

```
1 void readFileCombos(std::vector<FileCombo> &fileCombos) {
2     std::vector<ifstream> files(FILE_NAMES.size());
3     for (int i = 0; i < FILE_NAMES.size(); ++i) {
4         files[i].open(FILE_NAMES[i], std::ios::binary);
5     }
6
7     std::sort(fileCombos.begin(), fileCombos.end(),
8             [](const FileCombo &a, const FileCombo &b) {
9         if (a.fileId != b.fileId) {
10            return a.fileId < b.fileId;
11        }
12        return a.offset < b.offset;
13    });
14
15    for (FileCombo & fc: fileCombos) {
16        files[fc.fileId].seekg(fc.offset);
17        files[fc.fileId].read(fc.buffer, RECORD_SIZE);
18    }
19
20    for (ifstream & f: files) {
21        f.close();
22    }
23
24 }
```

Listing B.4. Our Level 3 (L3) Solution to Problem A

B.2 Problem B Solutions

```
1 void work(int start) {
2     for (int i = start; i < SIZE; i += THREAD_COUNT) {
3         for (int j = 0; j < INIT_SRC_VAL; ++j) {
4             --src[i];
5             ++dst[i];
6         }
7     }
8 }
9
10 void schedule() {
11     std::thread threads[THREAD_COUNT];
12     for (int i = 0; i < THREAD_COUNT; ++i) {
13         threads[i] = std::thread(work, i);
14     }
15     for (int i = 0; i < THREAD_COUNT; ++i) {
16         std::threads[i].join();
17     }
18 }
```

Listing B.5. Our Naive Level 0 (L0) Solution to Problem B

```
1 void work(int start, int end) {
2     for (int i = start; i < end; ++i) {
3         for (int j = 0; j < INIT_SRC_VAL; ++j) {
4             --src[i];
5             ++dst[i];
6         }
7     }
8 }
9
10 void schedule() {
11     int slice = SIZE / THREAD_COUNT;
12     std::thread threads[THREAD_COUNT];
13     for (int i = 0; i < THREAD_COUNT; ++i) {
14         threads[i] = std::thread(work, i * slice, (i + 1) * slice);
15     }
16
17     for (int i = 0; i < THREAD_COUNT; ++i) {
18         threads[i].join();
19     }
20 }
```

Listing B.6. Our Level 1 (L1) Solution to Problem B

C SCREENING SURVEY GIVEN TO PARTICIPANTS TO DETERMINE ELIGIBILITY

How much programming experience do you have?	
No experience	1
Less than 1 year	2
Between 1 year and 5 years (excluding)	3
Between 5 years and 10 years (excluding)	4
10 years or more	5
Do you have access to GitHub Copilot on VSCode?	
No	1
No, but I have applied	2
Yes	3
Are you employed by Open AI or Github, or were you involved with the development of Github Copilot?	
No	1
Yes, please explain:	TEXT_FIELD
Have you taken a systems course like Operating Systems, Distributed Systems, or Computer Networks?	
No	1
Yes, please enter the course title:	TEXT_FIELD
How familiar are you with the C++ programming language?	
Not familiar at all	1
Slightly familiar	2
Moderately familiar	3
Very familiar	4
Extremely familiar	5

Table C.1. Screening Survey

D TUTORIAL

Here we cover the details of details of the tutorial that the experimenter gave the participants before they were given the first programming problem.

The facilitator started sharing their screen and got confirmation that the participant could see the screen. They then demonstrated unzipping a ZIP file wherein a CPP was compressed and opening the uncompressed folder in VSCode. Following that, they checked that all VSCode extensions were disabled except for the Copilot extension for VSCode. The experimenter then opened their browser and showed that they could easily switch between their browser and VSCode. They also mentioned that participants are allowed to use their browser when solving either programming problem so there was no ambiguity as to whether they were allowed to use their browser or not. The experimenter activated Copilot and demonstrated using Copilot suggestions for the prompt “print hello world 8 times but on even times append an emoji”. The experimenter demonstrated accepting a suggesting, rejecting a suggestion, toggling between the next and previous suggestions, and then viewing all suggestions using the “Open GitHub Copilot” menu option.

They then demonstrated compiling the program with `g++ hello.cpp -o hello -std=c++17` and running the program. The facilitator stressed that `-std=c++17` must be used and that if participants were on a Linux machine or were using Windows Subsystem for Linux (WSL), they could add the `-lpthread` flag like so `g++ hello.cpp -o hello -std=c++17 -lpthread`. After compiling and running the program, the experimenter demonstrated zipping up the entire folder and sending the ZIP file via the online conferencing platform. The experimenter then demonstrated deactivating Copilot, closing VSCode and closing the browser used for the current problem. It was emphasized that this “cleanup” must be done after each problem is completed.

E PROGRAMMING SURVEYS GIVEN TO PARTICIPANTS AFTER SOLVING A PROBLEM

E.1 First Programming Survey

Have you seen this programming problem before?	
Prefer not to answer	1
No	2
Maybe	3
Yes	4
Have you solved this programming problem before?	
Prefer not to answer	1
No	2
Maybe	3
Yes	4
How well did you understand the programming problem?	
Prefer not to answer	1
Not well at all	2
Slightly well	3
Moderately well	4
Very well	5
Extremely well	6
How confident are you in your solution to the programming problem?	
Prefer not to answer	1
Not confident at all	2
Slightly confident	3
Moderately confident	4
Very confident	5
Extremely confident	6
How much time did you spend debugging your program (in minutes)?	
TEXT_FIELD	
How much time did you spend on your browser while solving the problem (in minutes)?	
TEXT_FIELD	
What resources did you use to help you solve the problem (i.e. StackOverflow, GeeksForGeeks etc.)?	
TEXT_FIELD	

Table E.1. First Programming Survey

E.2 Second Programming Survey

Table E.2. Second Programming Survey Plus Demographics

Have you solved this programming problem before?	
Prefer not to answer	1
No	2
Maybe	3
Yes	4
Have you solved this programming problem before?	
Prefer not to answer	1
No	2
Maybe	3
Yes	4
How well did you understand the programming problem?	
Prefer not to answer	1
Not well at all	2
Slightly well	3
Moderately well	4
Very well	5
Extremely well	6
How confident are you in your solution to the programming problem?	
Prefer not to answer	1
Not confident at all	2
Slightly confident	3
Moderately confident	4
Very confident	5
Extremely confident	6
How much time did you spend debugging your program (in minutes)?	
TEXT_FIELD	
How much time did you spend on your browser while solving the problem (in minutes)?	
TEXT_FIELD	
What resources did you use to help you solve the problem (i.e. StackOverflow, GeeksForGeeks etc.)?	
TEXT_FIELD	
What is your highest level of education at the moment (degree awarded/ongoing)?	
Prefer not to answer	1
Less than high school	2
High school graduate	3
Some college	4
2 year degree	5
4 year degree	6
Professional degree (Masters)	7
Doctorate	8
Other, please specify:	TEXT_FIELD

What is your current employment?	
TEXT_FIELD	
How familiar are you with Github Copilot?	
Prefer not to answer	1
Not familiar at all	2
Slightly familiar	3
Moderately familiar	4
Very familiar	5
Extremely familiar	6
How familiar are you with Visual Studio Code (VSCode)?	
Prefer not to answer	1
Not familiar at all	2
Slightly familiar	3
Moderately familiar	4
Very familiar	5
Extremely familiar	6
Have you taken a security course like Computer Security & Privacy, Cryptography, or Network Security?	
No	1
Yes, please enter the course title:	TEXT_FIELD
How familiar are you with the Python programming language?	
Prefer not to answer	1
Not familiar at all	2
Slightly familiar	3
Moderately familiar	4
Very familiar	5
Extremely familiar	6
How familiar are you with the Java programming language?	
Prefer not to answer	1
Not familiar at all	2
Slightly familiar	3
Moderately familiar	4
Very familiar	5
Extremely familiar	6

F LISTINGS OF PARTICIPANTS SOLUTIONS TO THE PROBLEMS

```
1 void schedule() {
2   thread threads[THREAD_COUNT];
3   for (int i = 0; i < THREAD_COUNT; i++) {
4     auto lambda = [i]() {
5       for (int j = i; j < SIZE; j += THREAD_COUNT) {
6         while(src[j].get()!=0) {
7           src[j]--;
8         }
9         while (dst[j].get() != INIT_SRC_VAL) {
10          dst[j]++;
11        }
12      }
13    };
14    threads[i] = thread(lambda);
15  }
16  for (int i = 0; i < THREAD_COUNT; i++) {
17    threads[i].join();
18  }
19  };
```

Listing F.1. P11's L0 Solution to Problem B with Copilot

```
1 void moveValues(int start, int end);
2
3 void moveValues(int start, int end){
4     int temp;
5     for(int i = start; i < end; i++){
6         temp = src[i].get();
7         for (int j = 0; j < temp; j++){
8             dst[i].operator++();
9             src[i].operator--();
10        }
11    }
12 }
13
14 void schedule() {
15     thread threads[THREAD_COUNT];
16     int thread_size = SIZE/THREAD_COUNT;
17     int start = 0;
18     int end = thread_size;
19     for(int i = 0; i < THREAD_COUNT; i++){
20         threads[i] = thread(moveValues, start, end);
21         start = end;
22         end += thread_size;
23     }
24     for(int i = 0; i < THREAD_COUNT; i++){
25         threads[i].join();
26     }
27 }
```

Listing F.2. P12's L1 Solution to Problem B with Copilot

```
1 void schedule() {
2     const int NUM_PER_THREAD = SIZE / THREAD_COUNT;
3     auto threadFunc = [ NUM_PER_THREAD](int index){
4         int start = NUM_PER_THREAD * index;
5         int end = min(NUM_PER_THREAD * (index+1), SIZE);
6         for (int j = start; j < end; j++) {
7             for (int k = 0; k < INIT_SRC_VAL; k++) {
8                 src[j]--;
9                 dst[j]++;
10            }
11        }
12    };
13    vector<thread> threads;
14    for (int i = 0; i < THREAD_COUNT; i++) {
15        threads.push_back(thread(threadFunc, i));
16    }
17    for (int i = 0; i < THREAD_COUNT; i++) {
18        threads[i].join();
19    }
20 }
```

Listing F.3. P17's L1 Solution to Problem B without Copilot

```
1 void schedule() {
2     thread threads[THREAD_COUNT];
3     for (int i = 0; i < THREAD_COUNT; i++) {
4         threads[i] = thread([&](int i) {
5             for (int j = i; j < SIZE; j += 4) {
6                 while (src[j].get() > 0) {
7                     src[j]--;
8                     dst[j]++;
9                 }
10            }
11        }, i);
12    }
13    for (int i = 0; i < THREAD_COUNT; i++) {
14        threads[i].join();
15    }
16 }
```

Listing F.4. P19's L0 Solution to Problem B with Copilot

```
1 void readFileCombos(std::vector<FileCombo> &fileCombos) {  
2     std::vector<int> file_descriptors;  
3     for( auto fname : FILE_NAMES ) {  
4         int fd = open(fname.c_str(), O_RDONLY);  
5         file_descriptors.push_back( fd );  
6     }  
7     for( auto &combo : fileCombos ) {  
8         lseek(file_descriptors[combo.fileId], combo.offset, SEEK_SET);  
9         read(file_descriptors[combo.fileId], combo.buffer, RECORD_SIZE);  
10    }  
11 }
```

Listing F.5. P22's L1U Solution to Problem A with Copilot

G TABLES OF THE CORRELATION MATRIX FOR PARTICIPANTS' DATA

	runtime	mode	time	understandProblem	confidentSolution	timeDebugging	timeBrowser	devExp	familiarCPP	familiarCopilot	familiarVSCode
runtime	1.00	0.46	-0.22	0.03	0.24	-0.15	-0.40	-0.39	-0.12	-0.01	0.21
mode	0.46	1.00	-0.58	-0.27	-0.22	-0.29	-0.72	-0.33	-0.48	0.04	0.01
time	-0.22	-0.58	1.00	-0.28	-0.26	0.67	0.75	0.17	0.33	-0.41	-0.33
understandProblem	0.03	-0.27	-0.28	1.00	0.59	-0.36	-0.06	-0.29	0.18	0.45	0.40
confidentSolution	0.24	-0.22	-0.26	0.59	1.00	-0.21	-0.09	-0.20	0.16	0.20	0.61
timeDebugging	-0.15	-0.29	0.67	-0.36	-0.21	1.00	0.52	0.18	0.19	-0.48	-0.28
timeBrowser	-0.40	-0.72	0.75	-0.06	-0.09	0.52	1.00	0.30	0.28	-0.09	-0.13
devExp	-0.39	-0.33	0.17	-0.29	-0.20	0.18	0.30	1.00	0.29	-0.23	-0.40
familiarCPP	-0.12	-0.48	0.33	0.18	0.16	0.19	0.28	0.29	1.00	0.08	-0.12
familiarCopilot	-0.01	0.04	-0.41	0.45	0.20	-0.48	-0.09	-0.23	0.08	1.00	0.13
familiarVSCode	0.21	0.01	-0.33	0.40	0.61	-0.28	-0.13	-0.40	-0.12	0.13	1.00

Table G.1. Correlation matrix for problem A

	runtime	mode	time	understandProblem	confidentSolution	timeDebugging	timeBrowser	devExp	familiarCPP	familiarCopilot	familiarVSCode
runtime	1.00	0.09	-0.21	-0.06	0.19	-0.04	-0.20	-0.30	-0.10	0.32	0.19
mode	0.09	1.00	-0.09	0.22	0.27	-0.34	-0.28	0.23	0.31	-0.04	0.05
time	-0.21	-0.09	1.00	-0.29	-0.21	0.62	0.67	-0.13	-0.08	-0.13	-0.19
understandProblem	-0.06	0.22	-0.29	1.00	0.42	-0.34	0.10	-0.06	-0.16	0.09	0.20
confidentSolution	0.19	0.27	-0.21	0.42	1.00	-0.26	-0.16	-0.02	-0.22	0.05	0.49
timeDebugging	-0.04	-0.34	0.62	-0.34	-0.26	1.00	0.49	-0.11	-0.13	-0.05	-0.10
timeBrowser	-0.20	-0.28	0.67	0.10	-0.16	0.49	1.00	-0.04	-0.26	-0.02	-0.21
devExp	-0.30	0.23	-0.13	-0.06	-0.02	-0.11	-0.04	1.00	0.29	-0.08	-0.31
familiarCPP	-0.10	0.31	-0.08	-0.16	-0.22	-0.13	-0.26	0.29	1.00	0.18	-0.06
familiarCopilot	0.32	-0.04	-0.13	0.09	0.05	-0.05	-0.02	-0.08	0.18	1.00	0.11
familiarVSCode	0.19	0.05	-0.19	0.20	0.49	-0.10	-0.21	-0.31	-0.06	0.11	1.00

Table G.2. Correlation matrix for problem B

```

1  int getChunkSize(int id) {
2      return ( SIZE / THREAD_COUNT ) + 1;
3  }
4  int getChunkStart( int chunk ) {
5      return chunk * getChunkSize(chunk);
6  }
7  int getChunkEnd( int chunk) {
8      return min (getChunkStart(chunk) + getChunkSize(chunk), SIZE);
9  }
10
11 void* workerFunc(void *arg) {
12     int id = (int64_t)arg;
13     int start = getChunkStart(id);
14     int end = getChunkEnd(id);
15
16     for (int i = start; i < end; i++) {
17         assert(src[i].get() == INIT_SRC_VAL);
18         assert(dst[i].get() == 0);
19         while ( src[i].get() != 0 ) {
20             if ( INIT_SRC_VAL > 0 ) {
21                 src[i]--;
22                 dst[i]++;
23             } else {
24                 src[i]++;
25                 dst[i]--;
26             }
27         }
28         assert( src[i].get() == 0 );
29         assert( dst[i].get() == INIT_SRC_VAL );
30     }
31     return NULL;
32 }
33
34 void schedule() {
35     pthread_t threads[THREAD_COUNT];
36     int createdThreads = 0;
37     for( int i = 0; i < THREAD_COUNT; i++) {
38         int err = pthread_create(&threads[i], NULL, workerFunc, (void*)(int64_t) i);
39         if (err != 0) {
40             // ... COMMENTED OUT SO NOT AFFECT CSV GENERATION
41             break;
42         }
43         // ... COMMENTED OUT SO NOT AFFECT CSV GENERATION
44         createdThreads++;
45     }
46     for( int i = 0; i < createdThreads; i++) {
47         int err = pthread_join(threads[i], NULL);
48         if (err != 0) {
49             // ... COMMENTED OUT SO NOT AFFECT CSV GENERATION
50         }
51     }
52 }

```

```
1 void do_work(int begin, int end) {
2     for (int i = begin; i < end; i++) {
3         while (src[i].get() > 0) {
4             src[i]--;
5         }
6         while (dst[i].get() < INIT_SRC_VAL) {
7             dst[i]++;
8         }
9     }
10 }
11
12 void schedule() {
13     std::thread threads[THREAD_COUNT];
14     auto amount = SIZE / THREAD_COUNT;
15     for (int i = 0; i < THREAD_COUNT; i++) {
16         threads[i] = std::thread(do_work, i * amount, (i + 1) * amount);
17     }
18     for (int i = 0; i < THREAD_COUNT; i++) {
19         threads[i].join();
20     }
21 }
```

Listing F.7. P27's L1 Solution to Problem B with Copilot